

Effect of rice planting method on azolla growth, in relation to water temperature and light intensity. Pattambi, Kerala, India, 1981 dry season.

Line plantings with two spacing combinations and two directions of lines were compared with equidistant planting (bulk method) to assure equal plant populations per unit area. Azolla was inoculated at 100 g/m² 1 wk after planting rice; azolla yield was measured 3 wk after inoculation.

Azolla growth was maximum with the bulk rice planting method (see table). That method registered the highest light interception and lowest water temperature (see figure). Planting method did not influence rice grain and straw yields. □

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Green manure as N source for flooded rice

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N content and rate of mineralization determine the efficiency of a green manure. Leguminous crops used as green manure differ in both respects. We evaluated *Sesbania aculeata*, sunn hemp (*Crotalaria juncea*), cowpea (*Vigna*

unguiculata), and cluster bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) as green manure for flooded rice.

Soil was a sandy loam, with pH 8.2, 0.34% organic C, and 0.06% total N. A basal dose of 26 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 25 kg K/ha as muriate of potash was applied before the last puddling.

Green manure crops were incorporated at 60 d, 1 d before transplanting long-duration rice variety PR106 at 15- × 20-cm spacing.

Influence of N through green manure on grain yield, N uptake, and apparent N recovery by rice, Ludhiana, India. Bars having a common letter are not significantly different.

No N fertilizer was applied to green manure plots; 2 treatments received urea applied at 60 and 120 kg N/ha and 1 treatment received no N. N supplied by the green manures was adjusted on a dry weight basis. Sesbania and sunn hemp were evaluated at two N levels.

Treatments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Plant samples collected at harvest were analyzed for total N.

Rice responded linearly up to 120 kg N/ha applied as urea (see figure). Yields

from green manure incorporated in amounts comparable to the N supplied by urea equaled or surpassed yields from urea. Cowpea and sunn hemp were the most efficient N sources, followed by sesbania and mungbean. □

Mineralization of fresh and dry azolla in the tropics

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We studied rate of mineralization of fresh and dry azolla under tropical conditions in two pot culture experiments in Jun and Sep 1984. The experiment was laid out in circular 0.1 m² cement pots. Each pot contained 20 kg air-dried soil; a 5-cm water level was maintained. Organic fertilizers were incorporated and thoroughly mixed with the soil (see table).

Soil and water samples were taken at 2-wk intervals to week 12, and ammoniacal and nitrate N contents estimated and expressed as mineralized

Effect of organic manure and time of incorporation (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 wk after incorporation) on percentage of mineralizable N. Kerala, India, 1984.

Organic manure	Mineralizable nitrogen (%)					
	2	4	6	8	10	12
5 t azolla/ha (13.4 kg N)	34.1	63.0	76.0	84.6	86.3	76.6
10 t azolla/ha (26.8 kg N)	26.0	43.6	40.7	47.7	57.8	61.2
Dry azolla equal to 5 t azolla/ha (13.4 kg N)	37.0	50.1	63.0	78.0	39.5	64.3
Dry azolla equal to 10 t azolla/ha (26.8 kg N)	33.3	35.6	50.5	44.9	20.5	35.6
5 t cattle manure/ha (26.9 kg N)	19.1	35.0	59.6	53.4	39.0	58.3
Green leaves of venga <i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> at 5 t/ha (25.4 kg N)	43.9	73.5	67.2	22.8	38.4	86.0

N. Percentages of available N to the quantity of N initially added were estimated by subtracting the N value of control from all treatments.

N release from 5 t fresh and dry azolla/ha compared with cattle manure and green leaves from week 6 to week 8. At that level, the highest available N was

86.6% from fresh azolla at week 6, 78.9% from dry azolla at week 8, 59.6% from cattle manure at week 6, and 86% from green leaves at week 12. In both fresh and dry azolla, 10 t/ha reduced and prolonged N release more than did 5 t/ha. At both levels, fresh azolla was slightly superior to dry azolla. □

Parthenium as green manure for rice

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We compared urea, wet leucaena, dry leucaena, parthenium, and sunn hemp in the main and succeeding irrigated lowland rice crops during 1984-85 wet and dry seasons.

Treatments to the main crop were in a randomized block design with three replications. No fertilizer was applied to the second rice crop.

Grain quality characteristics—optimal cooking time, swelling rate, gruel loss,

elongation rate, and palatability (color, smell, and taste)—were tested in both main and second crops.

Using parthenium as green manure had no effect on cooking and palatability characteristics. □

Physiology and plant nutrition

Supply and uptake of urea-¹⁵N by rice

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We studied the behavior of soil, fertilizer, and plant N in a greenhouse pot experiment where urea-¹⁵N was

applied to rice grown under permanent flooding.

The soil was a Crowley silt loam (Typic Albaqualf), 11% clay and 71% silt, with 7.0 g total C/kg, 0.8 g total N/kg, a cation exchange capacity of 9.4 meq/100 g soil; pH of 5.7 (1.1 soil/water ratio).

Air-dried soil (2.2 kg) ground to pass through a 1-mm mesh sieve was placed in polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pots (20 cm